

The Dilemma and Path Innovation of Education in Ethnic Minority Areas

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Abstract: Due to historical culture, natural geography, economic foundation and other reasons, the development of ethnic education still faces some special difficulties and outstanding problems, and the overall development level is relatively low. Education in some ethnic minority areas faces the real predicament of imbalanced educational resources, great shackles in traditional ideas, and difficulty in promoting education informatization. In order to accelerate the development of education in ethnic minority areas and achieve long-term peace and stability in the country, it is necessary to establish universal and special policies and promote long-term education mechanisms, and innovate the education path in ethnic minority areas in order to solve these dilemmas.

Key words: Minority education, Dilemma, Path innovation

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I. The Educational Difficulties in Minority Areas

1. Unbalanced educational resources

The biggest stumbling block in minority village education is the imbalance of resources. Generally speaking, the funding guarantee level and the per capita public funding standard for volunteer schools in ethnic minority areas are relatively low. Due to some historical and natural reasons, infrastructure construction also needs to be strengthened, and even basic education conditions in some areas are difficult to

guarantee. Compared with other regions, education resources are facing an uneven distribution of resources.

2. The traditional concept is greatly restricted

Traditional values are often hidden deeply. It has penetrated into the national spirit and penetrated into people's daily psychology. It is deeply entrenched in social culture and people's ideology and consciously affects the entire nation's value consciousness and values. Some ethnic minority areas adhere to the basic education education thinking of poverty alleviation based on the basic education and only the hardware but not the software, and the prevailing value of reading uselessness. Therefore, the value concept of reading uselessness still exists in some ethnic minority areas and people's psychology, which causes the dilemma of education development in ethnic minority areas.

3. Difficulties in promoting education informatization

Minority areas are generally located in remote areas, the traffic is not well developed, and the information is generally blocked. Education informatization is the shortcoming of education development in ethnic areas. As an important part of national informatization, educational informatization has a basic, strategic, and overall status, and is an indispensable support and driving force for the profound revolution in educational philosophy, educational reform, and teaching models.

II. Innovation of education paths in minority areas

Innovating education paths in ethnic minority areas, we must insist on narrowing the development gap, combining ethnic and regional factors, improving differentiated regional policies, zoning planning, classification guidance, consolidating the development foundation, narrowing the development gap, and promoting education equity.

1. Reasonable allocation of educational resources

Integrate the special funds of the National Education Central Committee and expand the scale of funds in a timely manner, and focus on solving outstanding problems in bilingual education, teacher training, national unity education, and ethnic cultural integration and innovation. The local people's governments at all levels should give preference to ethnic education when arranging financial transfer funds and financial resources at the same level. The counterpart support funds should continue to increase support for education.

2. Accelerate the promotion of education informatization

Accelerate the promotion of education informatization. Strengthen the construction of educational information infrastructure in ethnic areas, and accelerate the promotion of "broadband network school-school communication", "high-quality resource classes and classes", and "network learning space for everyone". The national education resource public service platform has priority to open to schools in ethnic areas.

3. Cultivate the endogenous impetus for the development of minority education

Pay more attention to the combination of releasing policy power and stimulating endogenous power. We will continue to increase the support of the central government

and stimulate local endogenous power, strengthen the top-level design, improve the policy system, increase investment, and build on the development advantages, accelerate the pace of development, and enhance the level of development.

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